

Tin(IV) and Titanium(IV) Derivatives of 2-Methoxyethanol

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2-Methoxyethanol complexes of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) have been synthesized and their probable structures on the basis of the ligand conformations have been discussed with the help of spectral data.

2-ALKOXYETHANOLS with regard to their various conformational forms have been extensively studied by ir spectra¹⁻¹¹. The literature reveals that not much is known about the behaviour of 2-alkoxyethanols when bonded to metal atom. These ligands were found to behave as a simple anion as well as a bidentate ligand when complexed to metals¹²⁻¹⁹. In the present work, the structures of the complexes of 2-methoxyethanol with tin(IV) and titanium(IV) have been deduced on the basis of the conformational features of the ligands.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under rigorous dry conditions. Solvents were dried by standard techniques. 2-Alkoxyethanols were purified as reported⁷. Stannic chloride was prepared by passing dry Cl_2 over tin metal. $\text{TiCl}_4(\text{BDH})$ was distilled (b.p. 136°) before use. Metal and halide were estimated gravimetrically. Electrical conductance was measured on a WTW conductivity meter in acetonitrile. Molecular weights were determined in boiling benzene with a semimicro Gallenkamp ebulliometer, employing a thermistor sensing and also determined cryoscopically in benzene for some of the products. The ir spectra have been recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 instrument as neat or nujol mull in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} and the solution spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 model in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} . Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

For the sake of brevity, the details of the reactions of metal halides MX_4 ($\text{M}=\text{Sn}$, $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br ; $\text{M}=\text{Ti}$, $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$) with 2-alkoxyethanols $\text{ROCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ ($\text{R}=\text{Me}$, Et) in different molar ratios have been summarized in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Under controlled experimental conditions metal halides react with 2-methoxyethanol to give compounds of the following types: $\text{SnX}_{4-n}\text{ROCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$

($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br ; $n=1$ or 2 ; $\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Et), $\text{MCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})$, $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ ($\text{M}=\text{Sn}$ or Ti), $\text{MCl}_{(4-n)}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_n$ ($\text{M}=\text{Sn}$ or Ti ; $n=2-4$) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OEt})_4$. The reaction conditions, the products and their analytical data and physical properties are summarized in Table 1.

Infrared spectral studies were carried out with a view to understand the mode of bonding of 2-methoxyethanol in the metal complexes. The CH_2 rocking modes in the region 800-850 cm^{-1} are characteristic of the conformation of the ligand¹⁹. For example, the band at 840 cm^{-1} is diagnostic of the *trans* behaviour^{20,21} of neat 2-methoxyethanol¹⁹. In the addition compounds of stannic chloride, SnCl_4 , $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, and in the trichloro derivatives, $\text{SnCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})$, $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ and $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})$, $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, all the spectral bands of 2-methoxyethanol can be noted suggesting the *trans* conformation of the ligands. The lowering of the band due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ indicates that the methoxyl oxygen of the added ligand is coordinated to the metal atom; this is also reflected in the pmr spectra wherein the considerable lowering of the positions of methoxyl protons in comparison to free alcohol can be noted (Table 2). The 1:1 and 1:2 tetrachloride adducts are found to be essentially non-electrolytes suggesting them to be the examples of 5- and 6-coordinate tin complexes. The most prominent bands at ~ 295 , 325-350 (vs, br) and at 275 (sh), 295-305 cm^{-1} (vs, br) arise from the $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ modes in 1:1 and 1:2 adducts respectively. This assignment which is not much unambiguous, on comparison reveals that these frequencies in 1:1 adducts are somewhat higher than found for the analogous 1:2 adducts indicating a lower coordination number (viz. 5) for the tin metal in 1:1 adducts. No further comment can be made about their stereochemistry at this stage. The trichloro derivatives, $\text{SnCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})$, $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ and $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})$, $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ are dimeric and show ir spectral similarity with 2-methoxyethanol indicating that both the ligand molecules are *trans*. The methoxyl protons give only one signal in the pmr spectra probably due

TABLE 1 - TIN (IV) HALO 2-ALKOXYETHOXIDE

S. No.	Products	Yield (%)	Methods of preparation	% M	% X	m. p, °C or sublimed at °C/mm	Molecular complexity
1.	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^*$	96	-15° in CHCl_3	28.76 (28.78)	34.39 (34.38)	62 sublimed to give No. 2	* *
2.	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{MeOH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^*$	72	Obtained from (1)	35.18 (35.29)	41.61 (42.15)	83 178-82/4.0	* *
3.	$\text{SnCl}_4(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}) \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	92	Reflux. C_6H_6 , Sod. salt method	31.50 (31.50)	27.20 (28.30)	149-52/0.2	2
4.	$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_2$	95	Sod. salt method	34.02 (34.90)	20.02 (20.90)	86	2
5.	$\text{SnCl}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_3$	92	Sod. salt method	31.53 (31.96)	9.10 (9.30)	87	2
6.	$\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	96	Reflux. C_6H_6	21.28 (20.17)	54.38 (54.10)	97 sublimed to give No. 7	* *
7.	$\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	68	Obtained from (6)	22.98 (23.04)	61.80 (62.10)	115-20/0.5	* *
8.	$\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{EtOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	92	Reflux. C_6H_6	19.21 (19.10)	51.90 (51.60)	110-115/0.8	* *
9.	$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}) \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	93	-10°C in CHCl_3	15.10 (15.60)	34.76 (34.87)	d	2
10.	$\text{TiCl}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_3$	90	Reflux. C_6H_6	16.00 (15.52)	11.78 (11.51)	d	2
11.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_4$	85	NH_3 gas is passed	13.69 (13.76)	—	d	2
12.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OEt})_4$	89	NH_3 gas is passed	12.10 (11.85)	—	d	1

* Insoluble in common organic solvents and soluble in MeCN. All others are soluble either in CHCl_3 or in MeCN.

** Ebulliometric measurements not possible as these loose HX on heating. Poor solubility prevented cryoscopic determinations.

detend to decompose between 75-100°/0.5 mm.

TABLE 2—PROTON NMR SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES DERIVED FROM 2-METHOXYETHANOL

S. No.	Compounds	$\text{CH}_3\text{-O}$ (τ)	-(O)-CH_2 (τ)	$\text{(CH}_2\text{-O)-CH}_2\text{-}$ (τ)
1.	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^a$	6.25	5.94 ¹	6.00 ₂
2.	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^a$	6.40	6.04 ¹	6.15 ¹
3.	$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}) \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^b$	6.30	5.52 ²	6.08 ²
4.	$\text{SnCl}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}) \cdot \text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}^a$	6.30	5.93 ¹	6.03 ¹
5.	$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_2^b$	6.55	5.85 ²	6.35 ²
6.	$\text{TiCl}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_3^c$	6.50	5.37 ²	6.24 ¹
7.	$\text{SnCl}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_3^b$	6.56	6.0-6.1 ²	6.40 ²
8.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_4^c$	6.70	5.70 ²	6.53 ¹
9.	$\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}^c$	6.54	6.05 ¹	6.14 ¹
10.	$\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	6.80	6.58 ²	6.58 ²

a=MeCN soln.; b= CDCl_3 soln.; c= CCl_4 soln. (TMS as an internal standard)

1=Sharp triplet; 2=Broad triplet; 3=Complex multiplet.

to the fast exchange of the methoxyethoxy moiety with the 2-methoxyethanol ligand. In view of the strong preference of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) to achieve coordination number six in various complexes it seems reasonable to assume that in these two derivatives dimerisation takes place through the alkoxy bridges to give an edge-shared bi-octahedral structure.

This is further substantiated by quantitatively determining the ratio $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})/\nu(\text{Ti-Cl})$, which comes out to be in the range 0.86-0.93 reported for the 6-coordinate complexes^{2,2}.

The dichloro- and monochloro derivatives of the $\text{SnCl}_{(4-n)}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_n$; $n=2$ and 3, monochloro derivative, $\text{TiCl}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_3$ and tetrakis-titanium 2-methoxyethoxide, $\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe})_4$ are dimeric and its spectral behaviour reveals the *trans* conformation of the ligand. This is further evinced by almost the unchanged position of $\text{CH}_3\text{-O}$ protons in pmr spectra (Table 2) as compared to free methoxyethanol consistent with the earlier reports^{14,19}. These are all likely to be 5-coordinate complexes.

($M = \text{Sn}$; $X = X' = \text{Cl}$; $X'' = \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}$);
 ($M = \text{Sn}$ and Ti ; $X = \text{Cl}$; $X' = X'' = \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}$);
 ($M = \text{Ti}$; $X = X' = X'' = \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OMe}$)

The dichloro-derivative of titanium could not be synthesized in the pure form. The steric factors seems to be important in preventing the methoxyethoxy moiety to act as a bridging ligand. This is substantiated by the fact that tetrakis-ethoxyethoxide, $\text{Ti}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OEt})_4$ is essentially monomeric 4-coordinate complex like titanium tetratert-butoxide²³.

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